

MULTISENSORY LANGUAGE TEACHING APPROACH AND THE VOCABULARY COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to measure the effectiveness of multisensory language teaching approach on improving the vocabulary competence in terms of word form, word meaning, and word use of students. Furthermore, it aimed to determine the difference in pretest and posttest scores before and after the implementation of the said approach. Using the one group pretest-posttest experimental research design, 30 Grade 10 students of Balele Integrated High School during the academic year 2020 – 2021 were conveniently selected as the respondents of the study. Pretest-posttest questions were utilized to obtain the data. Results of the pretest and posttest revealed that there was no significant difference between the students' vocabulary competence in terms of word form and word use before and after exposure to multisensory language teaching approach. On the other hand, there was a significant difference between the students' vocabulary competence in terms of word meaning before and after exposure to multisensory language teaching approach. It can be inferred from the results that teachers should look into the students' prior knowledge, their receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge. It is also noteworthy to consider first the students' various background, socioeconomic status, gender, intellectual ability, and learning style in determining their vocabulary competence.

Keywords: language learning, multisensory language teaching approach, vocabulary competence, Philippines